

Gurukul education system of ancient India and Indian education Policy Historical practice of 1947-2019 A.D.

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ABSTRACT

The Indian education system is the biggest challenge for today's time. The development and prosperity of the country increase only through the education system. After the independence of India, the governments of those times have also formed and reformed a new strategy in the education policy in parallel. Recently "Education Policy 2020" has been implemented. The education system that has just been started, we are trying to know anyway, through this revision article I want to tell about the ancient education system. It is only by education that human life gets knowledge in its life. In ancient times, had to go to Gurukul and Ashrams to get an education. We would all be very curious to know what we were taught in education at that time? Which areas were included in education? In those times, how was education imparted, and what effect did it have on human life? All these questions have been tried to reach you through this amendment.

Key Words: Ancient Education, Gurukul, Indian Education

Introduction

Ancient Indian civilization is one of the most interesting and important civilizations in the world. For proper knowledge of this civilization, it is necessary to study its education system, which protected, propagated and amended this civilization for more than four thousand years. Ancient Indians highly valued education. The great need for education was always accepted for physical and spiritual upliftment and for the proper fulfillment of various responsibilities. Right from the Vedic era, it was considered as a source of light, which illuminates various areas of human life and gives it the right direction.

Subhashit Ratnasandoh states that “knowledge is the third eye of man which helps him to know the origin of all the elements and shows the method of doing the right thing.” It is described in the Mahabharata that there is no asceticism like eye and truth like wisdom.¹

It is considered to be the means of salvation.² It has been said in the Subhashitratna Bhandar that the eye of knowledge that does not get rid of all the difficulties and obstacles of life is virtually blind. The ancient Indians strongly believed that intelligence gained and developed by education is the real

¹ नास्ति विद्या समं चक्षु नास्ति सत्य समं तपः ।
नास्ति राग समं दुःखं नास्ति त्याग समं सुखं ॥

² तत्कर्म यन्न बन्धाय सा विद्या या विमुक्तये।
आयासायापरं कर्म विद्यस्य शिल्पनैपुणम् ॥

power of man³. Various uses of learning have been described. It protects like a mother, employees in beneficial activities like a father, removes sorrow like a wife, brings joy, and expands fame and glory. It is as virtuous as imagined.

Vidya imparts humility, through humility comes eligibility (dexterity), through eligibility one obtains wealth, wealth brings righteousness and finally happiness comes. “Representing Vidya as the chief among all wealth, it is reported that neither the thief can steal, nor the brother can share, nor the king can snatch nor is it indelible to man. It is a type of wealth that increases even when spent.” The Brahmin is also devoid of knowledge, he is like Sood. After representing all the qualities related to learning, Indian humans proclaimed that a person devoid of knowledge is indeed an animal.⁴ In the view of ancient Indians, education was the means of all-round development of man.

Its purpose was not only to acquire booklet knowledge but also to develop the health of man. It is said that the priest of the scriptures is also foolish if he has not attained mastery as a working person.⁵ Through education, man gets the best means of livelihood. It was not desirable in the eyes of Indians to consider it merely as a means of livelihood. Those with such beliefs are condemned. In the view of ancient thinkers, education is a life-long thing with humans. A true teacher is one who remains a student till the end of his life. Thus, in the view of ancient Indians, education is the most important means of physical, mental, intellectual, and spiritual upliftment of a person.

Ancient education system of India

In the ancient education system of India, we find mention of both informal and formal educational centers. Formal education was imparted through temples, ashrams, and gurukuls while informal education was received through family, priests, pandits, sannyasis and festival themes, etc.

Gurukul education system

'Gurukul' literally means 'Guru's family' or 'Guru's clan'. The history of Gurukuls contains the history of India's education system and defense of knowledge science. In the development of Indian

³ बुद्धिर्यस्य बलं तस्य निर्बुद्धेस्तु कुतो बलम् ।
वने सिम्हो मदोन्मतः शशकेन निपातितः ॥

⁴ विद्या नाम नरस्य रूपमधिकं प्रच्छन्नगुप्तं धनं, विद्या भोगकरी यशःसुखकरी विद्या गुरुणां गुरुः ।
विद्या बन्धुजनो विदेशगमने विद्या परं दैवतं, विद्या राजसु पूजिता न तु धनं विद्या विहीनः पशुः ॥

⁵ शास्त्राण्यधीत्यापि भवन्ति मूर्खा, यस्तु क्रियावान् पुरुषः स विद्वान् ।
सुचिन्तितं चौषधमातुराणां, न नाममात्रेण करोत्यरोगम् ॥

culture, the beliefs of four Purusharthas, four varnas and four ashrams were interdependent for the accomplishment of their objectives, Gurukul was also a great seeker in their success. The Brahmins, Kshatriyas and Vaishyas, and Shudras were all children of Kulas, Varnas, and Samajas taken to the Gurukuls at 6, 8, or 11 years of age by the yajna and rites, and seated near the Guru and received education as Brahmachari. It is clear that the Gurukuls had an important role in the development of Indian civilization and culture.

Gurukul was a type of school in the ancient education system. The Gurukul system is an ancient education system. Gurukuls have existed since the Vedic era. Their main objective is to develop knowledge and they were highly focused on education. Gurus train their students with meditation, yoga, medicine, science, and other standards. It is well known that people from other countries like Europe, Middle East, and Portugal came to India to get a quality education. Today only a few Gurukuls are left in India. Students used to gather there and learn Vedas from their master. Students were treated equally regardless of their social standards. The students were considered a part of the Guru's family. Guru means teacher. The Gurukul system acquired a new tradition known as the Guru-disciple tradition. The teacher is called Guru and the students are called Shasya. The main objectives of the Gurukul system are:

- spiritual growth
- Self-restraint
- social awareness
- personality development
- intellectual development
- character building
- Protection of knowledge and culture
- Yoga
- Ayurveda
- Science

In the Gurukul system, students were divided into three categories, which are as follows

- Vasu- having attained education till the age of 24 years.
- Rudra - Educated till the age of 36 years.
- Aditya - Educated till the age of 48 years.

The Gurukul system was the only education system at that time. The students received their education with intensive education Not only education but they were also taught the essential aspects of their cultured and disciplined life. The students lived under the roof of Gurukul with brotherhood and lived humanity, love, and discipline. The Gurukul was a comprehensive learning center where students were taught good habits of respecting elders, mothers, fathers, and teachers. Overall, the ancient system gained great respect for this Gurukul system. Today, it is very regrettable to say that we are losing our culture. There are not even 300 gurukuls in India. There are only a few institutions like ISKCON that meet the criteria of Gurukuls. We are slowly moving towards western culture and they towards our culture. Today, only a small percentage of people know Sanskrit which is called the "language of gods".

Indian education system after the independence of India

During the 7 decades after independence, India's education system has developed gradually. From a literacy rate of 18% in 1951, we have grown to 73% by 2011. Currently, the education system in India is the strongest and largest in the world hosting over 315 million students. The education system started being influenced by various institutions. During the second half of the nineteenth century, the Theosophical Society of India and the Ram Krishna Mission began to merge Western ideals of education with Indian origin in order to inspire students and accept them universally. Intellectuals from various nationalities came together and helped shape the education system.

Indian education system after independence

India gained its independence from British colonial rule, the Indian education system, formerly accessible only to the elite, became available to the entire society. The government's Central Advisory Board established two committees - one for higher education and the other for secondary education - to address the challenges of education, formulate comprehensive education policies and improve the overall education landscape of the country. Currently, the Indian school system consists of four levels - pre-primary, primary, secondary, and higher secondary.

After the independence of India, India was a pathetic country in the field of education. There were only 400 schools, 19 universities, and more than 5000 students. Presently, education is going to touch a new height. Today our country has become 73% of Indian education (based on 2011 review) and we have the following facilities in the field of education.⁶

⁶ Higher education in India, Source - wikipedia.org

- More than 1.5 million schools
- 967 Total university of India
- More than 52000 colleges

To modernize the methods of knowledge delivery as per the needs of the 21st century generation, schools and universities are adopting various unique practices. These systems and innovative pedagogies have enabled educational institutions to develop the skill experiential learning

Experiential learning : Experiential learning is the process of learning through experience, and more specifically defined as "learning through reflection on doing". Hands-on learning can be a form of experiential learning but does not necessarily reflect the students own products of learners in such a way that they are capable of self-reliant and ambitious achievement. Some of these new age methods are: Experiential Learning, Peer Learning, The Rise of Ed-Tech, etc...

Indian education system committees

The Central Advisory Board of India decided to set up two committees, one responsible for university education and the other for secondary education.

1. University Education Committee (1948)

The first committee for the most important education in independent India was the 1948 University Education Committee, Radhakrishnan, which reported on the state of Indian university education and proposed reform and expansion. It is desirable to adapt to the future and future requirements of the country. The committee also aimed to establish universities that provide knowledge and knowledge for the development of overall student personality. This report suggested the reconstruction of the education system according to the Indian Constitution.

2. The Committee of the Midgate (1952–53)

The recommendations of the Mudaliar Committee have a very important place in the development of secondary education in India Independent. He stressed the need to train Indians democratically. Some reforms have been introduced into the Indian education system based on reports and recommendations, for example, starting higher secondary education courses with three-year curricula and opening vocational schools and colleges. More and more technology. Education has become the responsibility of the state and central governments.

3. Kothari Committee (1964–1966)

The Mudaliar Committee Appointed the Education Commission of India, known as the Kothari Committee, headed by D.Kothari. They have been mandated to deal with all aspects and areas of education and to advise the government on the development of the Indian education system.

National Education Policy of India

National Education Policy (1968) : According to the recommendations of this committee, the 1968 National Education Policy was formulated. The most important development in the reform of the education sector was national policy. Of education in 1968. In order to achieve the goal of cohesion and integration, the approach of education has been guided in all areas of society. The use of regional languages in secondary schools was encouraged to establish effective relationships between teachers and students. Indians were given excellence in schools as a means of education.

There was a feeling that education had the potential to act as a popular tool for social, economic and political change. Educational objectives are linked to long-term national aspirations. In addition, the government has established committees to study the development of modern education, especially since independence, leading to the conclusion that Indian education needs a fundamental reconstruction, almost a revolution. Goals and tackle various problems facing the country.

The National Education Policy Project of 1979 proposed the development of an education system that would not only help people improve their knowledge, but also hone their educational skills. Government functioning has changed. The main objective was to educate the students about ethics and ethics so that they can develop a good personality and become qualified citizens. It was suggested that a good educational system should be developed to promote constitutional values.

National Education Policy (1986): The 1986 National Education Policy emphasized reinvestment of the system to promote poor, adult education, gender equality, employment of teachers from oppressed groups and scholarships for persons with disabilities. Physical and mental health and areas requiring special attention. Development of special and new schools and universities as well.

All these political initiatives after independence have produced significant results in all fields, such as enrolment in school, increase in spending on education, increase in literacy rate, universalization of education, etc.

Reference

01. Dr. Sanjay Kumar Singh, “Prachin Bhartiya Sixa Pahdhati” (Hindi), Edition 2006, Hindustani Academy – Allahabad
02. Fischer, Steven Roger, "A History of Writing", 2004, Reaktion Books, ISBN 1-86189-167-9(PBK), ISBN 978-1-86189-167-9(HBK)
03. cmi, Kurian Kachappilly, www.academia.edu - Gurukula: A Family with Difference - An Exposition of the Ancient Indian System of Education – [Click Here](#)
04. Joshi, Ankur; Gupta, Rajen K. (July 2017). "Elementary education in Bharat (that is India): insights from a postcolonial ethnographic study of a Gurukul". [International Journal of Indian Culture and Business Management](#).
05. Joshi, Ankur; Bindlish, etc. "A Post-colonial Perspective towards Education in Bharat". Vision. 18 (4): 359–363. doi:[10.1177/0972262914552171](https://doi.org/10.1177/0972262914552171). ISSN 0972-2629.
06. Chandwani, Nikhil, The Times Of India – Article date : 08th March, 2019. “The importance of the Gurukul system and why Indian education needs it” [Click Here](#)
07. Atul Kumar, etc. "Prachin Bhartiya Sixa Padhdhati ki Vartman Samay me Naishamashikta” MAR-APR, 2019, VOL- 6/50, Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies ISSN - 2278-8808